

THE BIOCHEMISTRY AND MANAGEMENT OF ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE.

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ABSTRACT

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a generalized and progressive loss of (higher) mental function, affecting the ability to learn, remember, think, and reason, and the ultimate loss of all sense of time, place, and purpose. Although AD has been intensively studied for decades, the exact cause still remain elusive. However, scientists believe that genetic predisposition and environmental factors conspire with aging to trigger the onset of the disease. Early-onset (inherited) AD starts at about 65 years, and is caused by mutation of certain genes in chromosome 1, 14 or 21, while late onset (sporadic) which begins at age 65 years and above, has been linked to the activity of apolipoprotein E ϵ 4 gene in chromosome 19. The progressive cognitive and behavioural symptoms that characterize AD are derived from profound functional and structural changes observed in neurons. Early and accurate diagnosis of AD is important in order to provide counseling and treatment. The optimal approach to early detection of AD is clinical examination that incorporates evaluation protocols based on assessment of patient's cognitive abilities relative to past performance. At present there is no known cure for AD. Drug treatments such as antipsychotic medications and anti-depressants are given mainly to alleviate symptoms. As we await breakthrough in AD drug therapy, may our lot be a sound and respective old age coupled with intact memory, cognitive function, and wisdom.

KEYWORDS: Alzheimer disease, chromosome, cognitive function, presenilin, amnesia, aphasia.

INTRODUCTION

WHAT IS ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE (AD)?

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a generalized and progressive impairment of mental ability that interferes with normal social and occupational activities, that is, the progressive loss of higher mental function, affecting the ability to learn, remember, think, and reason, and the ultimate loss of all sense of time, place and purpose. AD account for 50% of irreversible dementia (Mera 1997; Selkoe 2001).

The progressive cognitive and behavioural symptoms which characterized AD are: amnesia - loss of recent memory, aphasia - difficulty in performing familiar tasks, agnosia – difficulty in recognizing people and object, aphasia – difficulty in language and communication, i.e. use and/or understanding words, orientation problems, not knowing what time, place and purpose, personality changes - anxiety, irritability, depression, restlessness, agitation, loss of initiative and others, aimless wandering; probably looking for a childhood home. (Mera 1997; Karla, 2001; Selkoe 2001).

ETIOLOGY

Although AD has been intensively studied for decades, the exact cause still remain elusive. However, scientists believe that genetic predisposition and environmental factors conspire with aging to trigger the onset of the disease (Hui-Xin, 2001).

Early-onset and late – onset AD represent the most easily recognized subtypes which can only be distinguished by the age of onset; early-onset AD normally begins at age 65, while late onset or sporadic AD starts at age 65 and above (Dennis, *et al.* 1999)

Early onset (inherited) AD is caused by mutation of certain genes in chromosomes 1,14 or 21. The chromosome 1 and 14 genes, presenilin-2(PS-2) and presenilin-1 (PS-1), are responsible for the familial early-onset AD. The PS-1 and PS-2 gene products are involved in APP processing, notch receptor signaling, protein trafficking and apoptosis. Although, the molecular mechanisms by which PS regulates these processes remain unknown, it is believed that due to missense mutation they probably influence the abnormal processing of APP to an insoluble fibrillar neurotoxic form called β -amyloid (Velez-pardo, *et al.*, 2000; Luca, *et al.*, 2001).

Chromosome 21 has the APP gene and mutation to this gene and/or extra copies of this chromosome (as in Down's Syndrome) can cause its over expression of APP and eventually excess production of β -amyloid.

Late - onset (sporadic) AD: Apolipoprotein E ϵ 4 gene (Apo E ϵ 4) in chromosome 19 have been implicated in the common and seemingly sporadic late - onset AD(Felix, *et al.*, 2000). The Apo E ϵ 4 gene product may function as a pathological chaperone in the AD pathogenesis since it influences abnormal APP processing into β -amyloid and its abnormal deposition as insoluble β -amyloid plaque (Yong, *et al.*, 2001).

Although several environmental risk factors have been suggested as possible causes of late onset AD, none has yet been convincingly identified.

Chemical toxins: Al, Cu & Fe are believed to exert effect on APP processing and promotion of β -amyloid deposition, and generation of reactive oxygen species (Micic and Petronijevic, 2001).

Dietary factor: Grant (1997) provided epidemiological evidence linking diet to AD development through modulating oxidative stress and inflammation. In the light of further studies, he proposed that high dietary fat and energy in old age are high risk factors while fish and cereals are risk reduction factors (Grant, 1999).

Brain injury: Although, yet to meet epidemiological criteria, head trauma leading to brain injury has been suggested. Such injury may cause primary destruction of brain tissues which may result in a cascade of cellular and pathological reactions associated with free radical generation. In this view, the capacity of confusive hemorrhage to induce free radical-mediated tissue damage suggests a rationale for the evidence linking head injury to a free radical related pathogenesis in AD (Ronald and Joseph, 2001).

PATHOLOGY

The progressive cognitive and behavioural symptoms which characterized AD are derived from profound functional and structural changes observed in neurons, their processes and synapses, and then microgliosis and astiocyctosis which accompany these changes (Ming and Hugo, 2000; Selkoe, 2001).

The pathological hallmarks of AD are large numbers of neurofibrillary tangles (NFTs) and plaques, which reflect neuronal degeneration and death in a specific neuronal population in the brain cortex, particularly, the hippocampus, parahippocampal gyri and the temporal and parietal cortices. (Ming and Hugo, 2000; Kurt and Christine, 2001).

Plaques are complex structures located extracellularly and consist of abnormal nerve processes, glial processes and a central amyloid core as well as aluminum silicates (Mera, 1997).

NFTs are located intracellularly and consist of insoluble fibrillar material called paired helical filament (PHF). The PHF is composed of collapsed cytoskeletal filaments, amyloid and tau. Tau is a complex microtubule associated protein with various intricately regulated functions. PHF tau is abnormally hyperphosphorylated via abnormal post translational processing by stress-activated protein kinases (JNK & p38) (Gail and Scott, 1999; Jin-Jing, *et al.*, 2001). Since NFTs are aggregates of PHFs formed from abnormal tau (PHF tau), little or no normal tau may be left to perform its normal microtubule associated functions, thereby resulting in the disruption of vital cellular processes.

Consequently, the affected neurons degenerate and die, ultimately producing the symptoms of dementia in AD (Trojanowski, *et al.*, 1999)

APP is a membrane bound protein made of about 616 amino acids. It is processed by at least 3 different proteases: β -secretase and γ -secretase cleavages release intact β -amyloid (1-42); the most fibrillogenic of the amyloid peptides. The α -secretase cleavage release sAPP α . (Mattson, 1997). APP intracellular domain (AID), the result of γ -secretase cleavage, acts as a positive regulator of apoptotic-mediated cell death. This implicates APP as a pro-apoptotic molecule involved in neuronal death in AD (Brent, *et al.*, 2000; Yoshikawa, 2000).

Current knowledge about APP function indicates that it is critically required for the maintenance of neuronal and synaptic structures and functions, so that its abnormal processing may cause it to lose its normal function and thus seemingly be involved in the etiology (primarily) of AD, while the fibrillogenic products (β -amyloid) of its processing could be involved in the pathology (secondarily) of AD (Susan, *et al.*, 2000). Aside pathological relevance, the biological role of APP proteolysis is unknown. (Brent, *et al.*, 2000).

Amyloid is an unusual fibrous glycoprotein complex derived from APP and deposited extracellularly in the brain. The principal component is the small protein called β -amyloid, a 42 amino acid peptide which is known to be neurotoxic, capable of causing neuronal dysfunction (Marwan, *et al.*, 2000; Servet, *et al.*, 2000). Recent studies have shown that treatment of cultured neurons with β -amyloid (1-42) evoked multiple consequences including generation of reactive oxygen species, hyperphosphorylation of tau, accumulation of cytosolic Ca²⁺ and apoptosis. Which of these events is the major cause of β -amyloid induced neurodegeneration has not been clearly defined.

DIAGNOSIS

Early and accurate diagnosis is essential in order to provide patient and family counselling and appropriate treatment, as they become increasingly available. Definitive diagnosis is possible through brain biopsy or through a brain autopsy. Brain biopsy is very rare because of the amount of tissues required to estimate NFTs and senile plaques in the brain. The optimal approach to early detection of AD is clinical examination that incorporates evaluation protocols based on assessment of the patients cognitive abilities relative to the past performance. Much of the assessment is by means of psychometric testing which encompasses the use of rating scales and test of memory and cognitive performance. This can be supported by electro-encephalography, computer tomography and functional imaging of the brain. Laboratory investigation may involve blood and cerebrospinal fluid examination to rule out chronic infections such as cryptococcal meningitis and syphilis as causes of dementia (Mera, 1997).

TREATMENT AND MANAGEMENT

At present there is no known cure for AD. Since AD has multiple molecular etiologies and a gradual, chronic evolution, one may anticipate several distinct classes of therapeutic molecules that could interfere with one or another step in the disease cascade (Selkoe, 2001). Drug treatments such as antipsychotic medications and antidepressants are given mainly to alleviate symptoms. Vasodilators are also employed to increase the brain -blood supply; these have mild effects in increasing alertness and decreasing confusion (Karla, 2001).

CONCLUSION

Since AD is a disease in which aging combine with multiple and synergistic molecular etiologies and diverse neuropathological cascade as well as overwhelming therapeutic problems mankind is only left to tremble at old age. No wonder, Alois Alzheimer described the disease as a riddle wrapped in a mystery inside an enigma.

However, as we live and anticipated a break through in AD drug therapy, may our lot be a sound and respectful old age coupled with intact memory, cognitive function and above all, wisdom.

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